

MINIMIZING HYGROTHERMAL EFFECTS ON THE DIMENSIONAL STABILITY AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE PLATES AND TUBES

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Abstract

Two related issues involving the effect of temperature, and moisture (hygrothermal effects) on composite plates and tubes were investigated. First, the results show the existence of a class of unsymmetric laminates which exhibit zero curvature changes (warping) with uniform changes in both temperature and moisture content. These laminates are non-warping yet still have strong [B] matrix coupling terms. The solution is generic, not dependent on the material used; and knowledge of the hygrothermal coefficients is not needed. Second, the effects of hygrothermal environment on the mechanical properties of tubes with tension-twist coupling was investigated. The theoretical results show that the laminate moduli (including the coupling terms) are very sensitive to the ply shear modulus, which is in turn affected by hygrothermal changes. Thus the laminate moduli are subject to large

changes with changes in environment. The largest changes occurred, as expected, for the hot, wet condition. Attempts to minimize these changes by altering the laminate configuration, while preserving the tension-twist coupling, were not successful when using a single composite material. However, a class of hybrid laminates was found which minimize, and in some cases completely eliminate, changes in laminate moduli, while preserving a significant amount of coupling.

PART I: DIMENSIONAL STABILITY

INTRODUCTION

The composite industry, in general, has shied away from using unsymmetric laminates because of the potential warping problems from changes in temperature or moisture content (i.e. Hygrothermal environment). It is the purpose of this paper to show that Non-Warping, Unsymmetric Laminates are possible.

This opens the door to designs which can, 1) take advantage of [B] matrix coupling terms, or 2) avoid adding unneeded composite plies just to force symmetry in a laminate.

The term "Unsymmetric Laminate" is taken here to be a laminate composed of one fiber/resin system, whose unidirectional layers contain some asymmetry in fiber orientation about the midplane of the plate. The term "**Warping**" is used to describe any change in curvature of a plate, either bending or twisting, due to changes in moisture content, and/or temperature. In addition, the changes in moisture content, and temperature are considered to be uniform, with no gradients.

In the past, many authors [1-4] have loosely stated that UNSYMMETRIC LAMINATES WILL WARP; this statement groups the set of warping laminates together with the set of unsymmetric laminates as the same set. This was done after observing warping in all unsymmetric laminates made at that time, and the fact that symmetric laminates did not warp. While it is easily proved mathematically, that symmetric laminates will not warp, no proof was ever given that unsymmetric laminates must warp. The pitfall in concluding that unsymmetric laminates will warp, is described in the following.

The laminated plate equation [3], relating thermal loads and moments ($\{N^T\}$, $\{M^T\}$) to the thermally induced inplane strains and curvatures ($\{\epsilon^T\}$, $\{K^T\}$), is:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N^T \\ M^T \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} AB \\ BD \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^T \\ K^T \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where A,B,D are the inplane, coupling, and bending stiffness matrices respectively. If a laminate is symmetric, then the terms $\{M^T\}$, and [B] are identically zero. This is because they can each be expressed as an integral of an ODD function over symmetric limits, which results in the zero numerical values. It then follows directly from Equation (1), that the thermal curvatures ($\{K^T\}$) must all be zero for a symmetric laminate. The following statements can then be made with certainty. **A) Symmetric Laminates will not Warp** and, **B) Warping Laminates are Unsymmetric**. Logically speaking, nothing can be concluded about the warping, or non-warping of unsymmetric laminates based on statements A) or B).

A particular need for non-warping unsymmetric laminates began when researchers in the helicopter field, were proposing rotor blades with Tension-Twisting Coupling. This Tension-Twisting Coupling was proposed with the intent to cause changes in the blades twist distribution with changes in blade tension, under a varying centrifugal load. Hong and Chopra [5] have also shown that tension-twist coupling, produced by unsymmetric fiber orientations within a blade, can have a significant effect on the stability of a rotor in hover, and can offer new aeroelastic tailoring parameters. While the structural geometry of many helicopter rotor blades is that of a box beam, many of the structural properties, and problems associated with this coupling will be

examined in the present work by modeling the blade as a flat laminated plate.

The present study is approached in three stages. First, the solution for non-warping unsymmetric laminates with tension-twist coupling is obtained for uniform changes in temperature only. Secondly, the solution is extended to include the effects of uniform moisture absorption. Finally, a general solution is obtained for a set of non-warping unsymmetric laminates which have all types of inplane-bending coupling (i.e. a fully populated [B] matrix).

ANALYSIS

1. Thermal Problem Formulation

The general linear laminated plate equation (1), can be written in expanded form:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ N_6 \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \\ M_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{61} & A_{62} & A_{66} & B_{61} & B_{62} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{21} & B_{61} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{62} & D_{21} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{61} & D_{62} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_6 \\ K_1 \\ K_2 \\ K_6 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where $\{N\}$ & $\{M\}$ and $\{\epsilon\}$ & $\{K\}$ are the stress resultants and moments, and midplane strains and curvatures, respectively from both mechanical and thermal effects. The B_{16} and B_{26} terms in Equation (2) are what produce the tension-twist mechanical coupling in the 1 and 2 directions respectively.

Equation (2) can be inverted to yield the compliance matrix, written in short as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon \\ K \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [\alpha] & [\beta] \\ [\beta^T] & [\delta] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Where $[\alpha]$, $[\beta]$, and $[\delta]$ the inplane, coupling, and bending compliance matrices respectively. Note that the terms $[\beta]$, and $[\beta^T]$ are the transpose of one another. For a rotor blade, or plate, to have tension-twist coupling, the β_{16} term must be non-zero. Hence, tension-twist coupling requires that:

$$\beta_{16} \neq 0 \quad (4)$$

This requirement (4) also stipulates that the laminate must be unsymmetric, since the $[\beta]$ matrix is identically zero for symmetric laminates. The effective thermal contribution, to the overall deformation of the plate, is obtained by first calculating the thermal stress resultants, and moments; given in (5) and (6) respectively.

$$[N^T] = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [Q] [\alpha] dz \quad (5)$$

$$[M^T] = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [Q] [\alpha] z dz \quad (6)$$

Where $[Q]$ and $\{\alpha\}$ are the transformed (rotation) stiffness matrix, and thermal expansion coefficients respectively; and z is the distance from the midplane of the plate. Using these and the compliance matrix, the thermal deformations $\{\epsilon^T\}$ and $\{K^T\}$ are obtained.

The second requirement of the plate, **Zero Warping**, stipulates that the thermal curvatures $\{K^T\}$ must be zero, from (3), (5), and (6), this is given by:

$$\{K^T\} = [\beta^T] \{N^T\} + [\delta] \{M^T\} = \{0\} \quad (7)$$

In this form the problem is quite complex, both $[\beta]$ and $[\delta]$ are functions of the material properties and stacking sequence of the laminate, while $\{NT\}$ and $\{MT\}$ have the added complication of including the transformed thermal expansion coefficients ($\{\alpha\}$). The unknown to be found in this development, is a **Particular Stacking Sequence** which satisfies both requirements (4) and (7). One could proceed in a brute force manner, and employ a computer to systematically try laminates with different stacking sequences until solutions satisfying both conditions (4) and (7) were found. However, even if solutions were found, one would be stuck with the particular amount of coupling (β_{16}) associated with each solution; and there would be no guarantee that these solutions would be non-warping under the effects of moisture absorption. Therefore, the solution was reformulated in an attempt to obtain an easier, more insightful solution.

Thermal Problem Reformulation

The actual cause of tension-twist coupling in unsymmetric laminates can be understood by considering a laminate with strong tension-twist coupling, for example: $(+\theta, -\theta)_T$. If the two halves of this laminate are considered independently ($+\theta$ and $-\theta$ on each side of the midplane), they are each symmetric in themselves, with zero tension-twist coupling of their own. Therefore, the only way to generate the coupling is through the interaction of these two halves. It is the A_{16} term of each half which produces the B_{16} coupling term of

the combination. When two of these laminates are joined, back-to-back, a non-zero B_{16} term is produced, which will give rise to the tension-twist coupling (β_{16}). The problem is that warping (twisting) may also be produced by this interaction, because each of the halves may deform in shear from a change in temperature, and/or moisture content.

Considering the interaction of the laminate halves in the previous example, a partial solution is postulated by a laminate "half" satisfying the following three conditions: 1) A symmetric laminate; 2) Zero thermally-induced shear strain ($\epsilon_6^T = 0$); and 3) A non-zero tension-shear coupling ($A_{16} \neq 0$, and hence $\alpha_{16} \neq 0$). This laminate "half" would have the property of undergoing a shear deformation due to an applied tensile (or compression) load, but would not shear due to a change in temperature. If these conditions can be met, the total solution is obtained by combining two of these laminates back to back to produce the tension-twist coupling (B_{16}) of the combination.

This combination would be thermally warp stable because: 1) The upper, and lower halves are each symmetric and in themselves thermally warp stable, 2) the thermal shear strain is zero for each half, so there is no thermal interaction between them to cause a thermal twist, and 3) the thermal expansion properties of the halves are matched, so that no thermal bending can occur.

With the three postulated conditions in mind, two facts about laminated composite plates are now added. First, for inplane thermal expansion isotropy, a

plate must have a minimum of two fiber directions, and be arranged with equal angle spacing, for example: $(0, 90)_s$. This implies that the thermal expansion is the same in all directions within the plane of the plate, hence the thermal shear strain is zero. This is true even if the laminate is rotated by an arbitrary angle (i.e. $\epsilon_6^T = 0$ for a $(\theta, \theta + 90)_s$ laminate, for all θ). Secondly, for inplane mechanical isotropy, a minimum of three fiber directions is needed, arranged with equal angle spacing, for example: $(0, 60, 120)_s$.

Considering these facts, one solution (laminate half) is self evident, it is a $(0, 90)_s$ laminate, rotated by an arbitrary angle θ (i.e. $(\theta, \theta + 90)_s$). This laminate satisfies the three conditions because: 1) it is symmetric, 2) it has zero thermally induced shear strain, because it has inplane thermal expansion isotropy, and 3) it has non-zero tension-shear coupling (A_{16}), because it is not mechanically isotropic in the plane ($\Theta \neq 0^\circ$, or 90°).

The $(0, 90)_s$ laminate is a very special laminate, in that it straddles the fence between inplane isotropic, and anisotropic behavior. It is mechanically anisotropic (inplane), and at the same time, isotropic in terms of inplane thermal expansion properties.

Thermal Problem Solution

One solution, for a laminate with tension-twist coupling, and zero thermal warping, is obtained by combining two of the half solutions back to back, given by:

$$[\theta, (\theta + 90)_2, \theta, -\theta, (-\theta + 90)_2, -\theta]_T \quad (8)$$

It should be noted that the stacking sequence solution (8) is valid for all angles " θ ", and is independent of the longitudinal, and transverse thermal expansion coefficients of the individual layers. There are also many variations on this solution that are also valid; for example:

$$[\theta, (\theta + 90)_2, \theta, \text{CORE}, -\theta, (-\theta + 90)_2, -\theta]_T \quad (9)$$

and

$$[\theta_n, (\theta + 90)_{2n}, \theta_n, -\theta_n, (-\theta + 90)_{2n}, -\theta]_{mT} \quad (10)$$

where $n = 1, 2, 3 \dots$ $m = 1, 2, 3 \dots$

In addition, an oddity occurs in these solutions (8), (9), and (10) when $\theta = 45^\circ$. The resulting laminate is unsymmetric, non-warping, and the entire [B] matrix is zero.

These solutions can be easily extended to produce thin wall tubes with tension-twist coupling, which will not twist with changes in temperature. One stacking sequence which would provide this is used as the tube wall.

$$(\theta, \theta + 90)_T \quad (11)$$

2. Hygrothermal Curvature Stability

The reformulation of the previous problem, in terms of warping due to moisture absorption, is identical to that of the thermal problem, except that ΔT and $\{\alpha\}$ terms are replaced by c and $\{\beta\}$ terms; which are the specific moisture concentration and the moisture swelling coefficients, respectively. Therefore, since the previous solution is independent of the thermal expansion coefficients of the individual layers, it is also independent of the moisture swelling coefficients. Hence, the previous

solutions (8), (9), and (10) are hygrothermally curvature stable (non-warping). Laminate stacking sequence solutions of this type are Hygro-Thermally Curvature stable Coupling (HTCC) laminates.

A general proof, that laminates of the type given above are **non-warping**, ($\{K^T\} = \{0\}$) and have **non-zero, tension-twist coupling** ($\beta_{16} \neq 0$) is given in Reference [6].

HTCC Laminate Coupling Strength

The magnitude of the coupling terms for the HTCC laminate must be addressed to determine if much is lost by using this configuration. For comparison, a $(\theta_4, -\theta_4)_T$ laminate, which is known to have strong (β_{16}) coupling, is compared to the HTCC (Equation 8) laminate. The material properties used are those for T300/5208 graphite/epoxy [3]. The parameter which is relevant to tension-twist coupling is β_{16} . Figure 1 shows the plot of β_{16} versus θ for both laminates. The tension-twist coupling (β_{16}) of the HTCC laminate is very strong, its maximum being only 15% less than that of the $(\theta_4, -\theta_4)_T$ laminate.

3. Other [B] Matrix Coupling Terms

Possible Using The HTCC Concept

The HTCC laminates developed so far, were aimed at hygrothermal curvature stability in unsymmetric (actually antisymmetric) laminates with tension-twist coupling. Using the same reasoning as the previous development, the upper and lower ply groups do not have to be antisymmetric with respect to each other in order to be non-warping. However, other [B] matrix terms become

active. By using two independent angle parameters (θ^1 , & θ^2), a more general HTCC laminate results:

$$[\theta^1, (\theta^1 + 90)_2, \theta^1, \theta^2, (\theta^2 + 90)_2, \theta^2]_T \quad (12)$$

Figure 1
Tension-Twist Coupling Compliance
for HTCC and
Antisymmetric Laminates

By adjusting θ^1 and θ^2 , it is now possible to obtain a fully populated [B] matrix while maintaining hygrothermal curvature stability (zero warping). For example, tension-bending coupling could be obtained by using a $[+45, -45_2, +45, 0, 90_2, 0]_T$ HTCC laminate.

The laminate given by (12) can have a fully populated [B] matrix, however, there are only two independent quantities. The terms within the [B] matrix, for this laminate, have the following relationships:

$$B_{11} = B_{22} = -B_{12} = -B_{66} \quad (13)$$

$$B_{16} = -B_{26} \quad (14)$$

Plots of B_{11} and B_{16} (using T300/5208, graphite/epoxy) versus θ^2 , using θ^1 as a parameter, are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2
Compliance Stiffness (B_{11})
for the HTCC Laminate with
Two Independent Ply Groups

Figure 3
Compliance Stiffness (B_{16})
for the HTCC Laminate with
Two Independent Ply Groups

Extending the HTCC concept to an even more general form results in a laminate with "n" independent angles ($\theta^1, \theta^2, \theta^3, \dots, \theta^n$), and is given by:

$$[\theta^1, (\theta^1 + 90)_2, \theta^1, \theta^2, (\theta^2 + 90)_2, \theta^2, \theta^3, (\theta^3 + 90)_2, \theta^3, \dots, \dots, \theta^n, (\theta^n + 90)_2, \theta^n]_T \quad (15)$$

For example, it is not obvious, although it is true that the laminate defined by:

$$(10, -80_2, 10, -42, 48_2, -42, 75, -15_2, 75)_T \quad (16)$$

is Hygrothermally curvature stable. It will not warp from moisture content or temperature changes (steady state, no gradients), and the [B] matrix is fully populated.

HTCC SUMMARY

- 1) HTCC laminates make possible strong [B] matrix coupling terms, while maintaining hygrothermal curvature stability (i.e. Zero Warping).
- 2) The hygrothermal curvature stability of the HTCC laminates is independent of the hygrothermal properties of the individual lamina. The thermal expansion, and moisture swelling coefficients are not needed for a solution.
- 3) The magnitude of the [B] matrix coupling terms are a continuous function of the angle parameters (θ 's), between zero and their upper limit.

PART I: CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusion of the work presented, is that *Non-Warping Unsymmetric Laminates are Possible*. This can enable designers to consider applications for unsymmetric laminates without worrying about hygrothermal warping. Applications could include both investigating uses for the [B] matrix coupling terms; as well as eliminating the need to add layers of material, in a particular design, just to have a symmetric laminate.

Unsymmetric laminates represent a large, and important design resource; and to date, relatively untapped. Work needs to be done to open this resource, and use it in regular design practice.

PART II:
HYGROTHERMAL EFFECTS
ON PROPERTIES

The emphasis of this work was to study the effects that hygrothermal environment has on the tension-twist coupling and other elastic moduli of composite tubes. The environment influences the temperature and moisture content of composite materials which primarily affect the matrix of the material; the fibers are resistant to their influence [3]. The goal of this research was to develop blade laminates which possess the desired coupling but which exhibit minimal variations due to hygrothermal effects [7].

Many current rotor blades use 0° fibers to provide bending stiffness and $\pm 45^\circ$ fibers for torsional stiffness. In this configuration, the bending and twisting modes are *fiber*-dominant and, as such, do not show much variation due to hygrothermal effects. However, these blades do not possess the desired coupling which depends on *matrix*-dominant modes. Blades which are tension-twist coupled may therefore exhibit a greater dependence on hygrothermal effects than conventional blades.

The emphasis of the theoretical work was to find laminates which possess minimal variation in coupling due to hygrothermal effects. This is done by

defining a model for the effects and introducing this into the derivation of coupling. The coupling is then studied with the goal of removing the hygrothermal effects. The proposed method of reducing the effects is based on intuitive reasoning. For example, if the primary influence on coupling is shear modulus, then adding fibers in directions suitable for reducing shear effects may also reduce hygrothermal dependence and this reduction may be obtainable without eliminating coupling.

1. CLT and the Thin-Walled Tube

Classical laminated plate (CLT) provides the theoretical basis for this work by providing a method by which the properties of a laminate (i.e., the laminate modulus and compliance) may be found from the properties of the individual plies.

Assumptions may be made to simplify CLT when applied to thin-walled circular cylinders. Only inplane strains are allowed; curvatures induced by the moments are forced equal to zero. Therefore, there can be no curvatures consistent with CLT. A torque about the tube axis manifests in the CLT analysis as an inplane shear stress.

2. Tension-Twist Coupling in Tubes

The desired coupling is one in which an axial force applied to a circular tube will create a twisting response in the tube. For the tube-wall laminate this becomes a coupling between extension and shear. When the only load applied to the tube is an axial force, P , the laminate compliance relation is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{16} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{26} \\ a_{16} & a_{26} & a_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

Where ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , ϵ_6 are the inplane strains, a_{ij} is the inplane compliance matrix, and N_1 is the axial stress resultant [3]. The shear strain, which creates twist, is now $\epsilon_6 = a_{16}N_1$. The axial stress resultant N_1 , is the applied load distributed over the perimeter of the tube end, or $N_1 = P/2\pi r$ for a thin-walled tube of radius r . Assuming small displacements, the angle of rotation ϕ of a cross section of the tube as a function of the strain is

$$\phi = -\frac{\epsilon_6 \ell}{r} \quad (18)$$

where ℓ is the tube length. The twist rate, $\phi' = \phi/\ell$, is

$$\phi' = -\frac{a_{16}}{2A} P \quad (19)$$

where A is the cross-sectional area enclosed by the midplane of the tube wall.

The amount of twist produced by an axial force applied to a composite tube is a function of the a_{16} term in the compliance matrix. Given a fixed tube geometry, this is the only available parameter which governs twist rate.

3. Hygrothermal Effects

The temperature and moisture content of a composite structure are affected by the environment to which it is subjected and may be placed under the single category of hygrothermal (or HT) effects. These environmental parameters affect the constituent material properties of the structure which in turn affect its structural characteristics.

The matrix of a composite material is

much more strongly affected by HT environment than are the fibers. For this reason, HT effects on the fiber direction stiffness property (Q_{xx}) are considered to be insignificant when compared to effects on ply transverse and shear stiffnesses Q_{yy} and Q_{ss} respectively.

In the theoretical work, the effects of hygrothermal environment are limited to the shear modulus. The effects of small variations in shear modulus on the coupling are significantly larger than those of the other material properties. The effects of temperature and moisture content are lumped into a single variable, η . This variable is used as a modifier of the shear modulus such that

$$Q_{ss} = \eta(T, c) \bar{Q}_{ss} \quad (20)$$

in which \bar{Q}_{ss} is some reference value of the shear modulus such as for room temperature, dry conditions.

If more than one material is used in a laminate, it will be assumed that all shear moduli exhibit the same variation due to HT effects. There is only one η no matter how many materials are involved. This is based on the assumption that these laminates will have only one matrix material and that matrix behavior determines hygrothermal dependence.

The approach to reducing the effects of hygrothermal environment on the tension-twist coupling of tubes is based on intuitive reasoning. Since the shear effects are most important, fibers are placed in directions so as to oppose shear effects. This will be detrimental to the coupling as it will stiffen the lami-

nate in shear. However, a compromise may be found which retains a useful amount of coupling while reducing the hygrothermal effects. For the family of laminates based on $[\Theta/\Theta+90]_T$, this means adding $\Theta \pm 45$ fibers to the laminate. The appropriateness of this scheme is examined in the following section.

4. Laminate Development

For a general laminate, a change in temperature may produce a shear strain which will cause a structure to deform. It is useful to work with laminates which will not exhibit thermally-induced shear deformation. One family of laminates with this property (independent of material properties) but which exhibits extension-shear coupling has the form $[\Theta\Theta + 90]_{mT}$ from Part I equation 11. Also, groups of plies each with this form but composed of different materials or with different orientations, Θ , may be stacked together without affecting this behavior.

In order to allow for more flexibility, a new laminate is considered which incorporates shear stabilizing plies. This laminate is given by

$$\left[(\Theta/\Theta + 90)_{\zeta_G^G} / \Theta \pm 45 \right]_{\zeta_F^F} T \quad (21)$$

is composed of two groups of the previous type, one rotated away from the other by 45° . To provide additional freedom, these two groups may be composed of different materials as indicated by the superscripts G and F. The terms ζ^G and ζ^F are the thickness ratios of the two materials used and $\zeta^G + \zeta^F = 1$.

In order to investigate the effect of various ζ^F ratios on the hygrothermal sensitivity of the laminate coupling (a_{16}), the compliance matrix (a_{ij}) must be calculated for the hybrid laminate, including a ply shear stiffness modified by η .

Rather than casting this as an optimization problem to minimize $|\partial a_{16} / \partial \eta|$, a ζ^F for which $\partial a_{16} / \partial \eta = 0$ is sought. This results in a cubic equation for ζ^F , where the coefficients (C_3, C_2, C_1, C_0) are functions of the material properties and η .

$$c_3(\zeta^F)^3 + c_2(\zeta^F)^2 + c_1 \zeta^F + c_0 = 0 \quad (22)$$

While the solution of the cubic equation for ζ^F for the general case of any two materials is difficult, it is easy to solve if specific materials are chosen for G and F. Because, even for two specific materials, the coefficients c_3, c_2 , and c_1 are quadratic functions of η , ζ^F is still a function of the hygrothermal environment. In general, it is not possible to find one ζ^F which exactly satisfies the requirements for this laminate at all values in the desired range of η . However, for most materials, in which $Q_{ss} \ll Q_{xx}$, the order of the coefficients for η^2 will be significantly less than for the η terms, which are of smaller order than the constant terms. Therefore, it may be expected that the final solution for ζ^F will not be strongly dependent on η .

The nature of the cubic equation is such that it will typically have one real root and a pair of complex conjugate roots. The complex roots may be ignored. If the real root is outside the range

$0 \leq \zeta^F \leq 1$, then there would be no realizable configuration in which hygrothermal conditions did not effect coupling. The laminate would probably need to be composed entirely of one of the two materials involved to minimize the effects. For all of the materials used in this analysis, this was not a problem; all had a single real root within the range of 0 to 1.

The solution of the equation for ζ^F for $G=T300/5208$ and $F=Scotchply 1002$ is shown in Figure 4 (material properties from ref. 3). The discrete data points in the figure indicate the real solution of the cubic equation for specific values of η . It is important to note that, while the graph shows values for $0 \leq \eta \leq 1.25$, the experiments performed show that the actual range of interest for η is $0.80 \leq \eta \leq 1.05$. The upper limit of this range depends on the value of η at which \bar{Q}_{ss} is defined.

Figure 4
Thickness Ratio Required
For Zero Hygrothermal
Effects on Coupling

There is one type of laminate in this family for which ζ^F is not a function of η . When G and F are the same material, then, in order for the laminate to be HT-independent, $\zeta^F = 1/2$.

However, this produces the laminate $[(22.5/5 - 67.5)/(-22.5/67.5)]_{mT}$, which has no coupling and is, therefore, not of interest. Hybrid laminates must be used to provide coupling which is hygrothermally immune.

The remainder of this analysis will concentrate on the materials $G=T300/5208$ and $F=Scotchply 1002$. It is now possible to look at the actual coupling produced and also the effects on the other terms in the compliance matrix. For this analysis, the terms will be found based on the assumption that $\Theta = 22.5^\circ$, the condition that produces maximum coupling. The coupling a_{16} for a range of η seen in experiments is almost constant for $\zeta^F = 0.77$. A comparison of the coupling for this laminate with those for single-material $[22.5/-67.5]_{mT}$ laminates made of G and F is shown in Figure 5. Note that both the graphite and fiberglass laminates have several times the coupling of the hybrid laminate but also exhibit significantly more HT sensitivity. Since coupling is the inverse of stiffness, the hybrid laminate is stiffer in coupling than the single-material laminates.

Figure 6 shows the sensitivity of the compliance term (a_{11}) for $\zeta^F = 0.77$ hybrid laminate with the single-material laminates. The hybrid laminate shows improved immunity from HT effects over the single-material laminates; a laminate not optimized for effects in terms other than a_{16} also improves performance for the other compliance terms of these coupled laminates. This trend is shown for the compliance terms a_{12} and a_{66} as well.

Figure 5
Comparison of a_{16} for
Hybrid and Single-Material
Laminates

Figure 6
Comparison of a_{11} for
Hybrid and Single-Material
Laminates

PART II:

CONCLUSIONS

1. The extension-shear coupling of a laminate is dominated by the shear moduli of the constituent materials. Hygrothermal effects may be modeled through shear modulus variations.
2. Theoretical results show that it is possible to design hybrid laminates with extension-shear coupling which exhibit negligible variation in coupling due to hygrothermal effects.

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